

Climate seasonality shapes functional diversity of Afrotropical bird communities across spatial scales.

Andres Angulo-Rubiano¹, Dylan Craven^{2,3}, Francis Njie Motombi⁴, Sergei Bobo Kadiri⁵, Holger Kreft⁶, Matthias Waltert¹

² GEMA Center for Genomics, Ecology & Environment, Universidad Mayor, Santiago, Chile

³ Data Observatory Foundation, Santiago, Chile³ Functional Ecology and Biogeography, GEMA

⁴ Mount Cameroon National Park, 563F+2V, Buea, Southwest Region, Cameroon

⁵ Department of forestry, Laboratoire de Faune, Aires Protégées, Sylviculture et Technologie du Bois, University of Dschang, Cameroon

⁶ Biodiversity, Macroecology & Biogeography, Faculty of Forest Sciences and Forest Ecology University of Göttingen, Büsgenweg 1, 37077 Göttingen, Germany

Abstract

Aim: How does the functional facet of animal communities respond to climatic gradients in the tropical lowlands is not well understood with implications for predicting futures trajectories of functional diversity. We assessed the effects of climatic factors and their seasonalities on the functional structure and diversity of tropical rain forest bird communities in a regional climatic gradient to investigate if they respond in divergent ways to climate and whether the effect is mediated by species richness and spatial scale.

Location: Central Africa (Cameroon)

Time Period: Two years

Major Taxa Studied: Birds

Methods: We used 144 ten-minute point counts allocated in four distant locations (> 300 km, 36-point counts per location) representing different climatic and floristic clusters from a tropical lowland climatic gradient. We used nested linear mixed effect models to test the effects of four climatic covariates (precipitation, temperature and their seasonalities) on different facets of functional diversity (functional dispersion, functional evenness, Hill functional diversity). We explored functional structure using community weighted mean values. To evaluate the influence of richness on functional diversity we computed standardized effect sizes. Based on the fractal structure we explored climatic effects across four sampling scenarios where spatial extent is the same, while effective spatial grain varies differentially

Results: Bird community functional structure revealed distinctive trait syndromes under different precipitation regimes. Functional facets responded divergently to climate, with precipitation seasonality and temperature exerting stronger and more consistent effects than mean climatic conditions. Relationships were robust across spatial scales, with functional richness metrics showing higher sensitivity to richness than other metrics.

Conclusion: Our results suggest that the functional facet of tropical lowland animal communities respond divergently to rainfall and temperature seasonality suggesting the operation of distinctive abiotic filters, selecting for unique trait animal syndromes. These syndromes imply differential functional vulnerability to future changes in climate seasonality underscoring the need to move beyond mean climatic conditions when exploring future trajectories of functional diversity.

1. Introduction

Functional diversity reflects the extent of change in traits among populations and species and has been the focus of extensive research in the last decades (de Bello et al. 2025; Violle et al. 2014). The functional dimension of biodiversity matters because traits define the responses of species to environmental conditions and its influence on ecosystem functioning (Diaz and Cabido 2001; Lavorel and Grigulis 2012). Therefore, understanding how functional diversity changes (responds) across directional changes in environmental conditions (environmental gradients) is of prime importance to predict and anticipate the effects of global environmental change (de Bello et al. 2025).

How functional diversity of ecological communities responds to complex regional environmental gradients in tropical lowland rainforest regions is not well understood. While the responses of functional diversity to different environmental gradients is rather well known, especially in temperate regions (Graco-Roza et al. 2022), most of the research of the responses of functional diversity in the tropics was focused in altitudinal gradients (Hanz et al. 2019; Horak et al. 2019) or latitudinal gradients (Swenson et al. 2017) with few examples from tropical lowlands and particularly focused on beta diversity, fragmented forests and gradients with different land uses (Echeverri et al. 2019; Gomez et al. 2020). Afrotropics are not well explored for functional diversity (Graco-Roza et al. 2022), with few studies in altitudinal gradients (Horak et al. 2019; Pernice et al. 2025; Vollstaedt et al. 2017), but no studies of the functional diversity and structure of animal communities in the Congolian rainforest in central Africa. This underscores the need to explore how the functional diversity and structure of Afrotropical communities change along climatic gradients where altitude and temperature do not present large variation.

One central aspect about functional diversity and structure is that different facets of functional diversity can respond in very different ways to environmental gradients (de Bello, Carmona, et al. 2021a; Mason et al. 2013). Some research has explored in tropical regions multiple metrics of functional diversity in altitudinal gradients and showed contrasting responses (Hanz et al. 2019; Pernice et al. 2025). However, it's not clear how different facets (richness, regularity, evenness) (Mammola et al. 2021) change with climatic conditions when they are evaluated at multiple spatial scales in the tropical lowland gradients. Therefore, exploring these responses can provide a mechanistic basis for predicting the trajectory of animal communities under different climate change scenarios.

It is expected that precipitation positively influences different facets of functional diversity via direct and indirect effects on primary producers and metabolic responses (Albrecht et al. 2018; Li et al. 2022), potentially enhancing both the occupation of the trait space (richness) and the variability of traits (regularity) (Zuo et al. 2021). The responses of evenness to abiotic factors are less clear with both positive or negative responses (de Bello, Carmona, et al. 2021). In contrast, is less understood how climatic seasonality influences different facets of functional diversity of tropical animal communities. Increased climatic seasonality might intensify harsh abiotic filtering, selecting for species with similar trait values to cope with temporal fluctuations (Wieczynski et al. 2019) reducing trait variability (divergence) and functional richness, while increasing a regular occupation of the trait space (evenness). Another possibility is that more stability in climatic conditions means the persistence of more species (high taxonomic diversity) (Buckley et al. 2024; Xu et al. 2023) with concomitant increases of species having more different traits via sampling effects (Naeem and Wright 2003) enhancing different facets. However, these hypotheses have rarely been tested in tropical regions and far less in lowland climatic gradients.

Equally unexplored in tropical regional gradients is how the functional structure of animal communities' changes with seasonality and mean climatic values expressing unique trait combinations (trait syndromes) (de Bello, Carmona, et al. 2021; Díaz et al. 2016). Previous studies using metrics that explore functional structure such as community mean trait values (CWM) show different plant functional strategies along rainfall gradients (Durán et al. 2019; Muscarella and Uriarte 2016). However, it's less clear if the functional structure of tropical animal communities measured by CWM also shows consistent changes and particular trait syndromes along these gradients with few studies exploring these changes (Gorczynski et al. 2021).

A relevant issue for exploring the relationship between functional diversity and climate is to understand how taxonomic diversity influences functional diversity in the sense of disentangling their response to environmental gradients (Cadotte and Tucker 2017; de Bello, Carmona, et al. 2021a). A proposed solution is to account for species richness developing null models, the so-called (Standardized effect sizes) (Cadotte and Tucker 2017). This can provide a robust way to explore how functional diversity metrics respond to climatic factors after controlling for richness influence and in this way revealing underlying assembly mechanisms.

Finally, it is well established that spatial scale influences diversity responses (Chase et al. 2019; Simpson and Pearse 2021; Wiens 1989). However, it's poorly understood how this scaling changes the response of functional diversity and structure in tropical climatic gradients. Therefore, using sampling designs that allow multi-scale assessment of diversity (Marsh and Ewers 2013; Simpson and Pearse 2021) will prove critical for exploring how changes in spatial scale influence the effects of climate on functional diversity.

The objective of the present work is to make an evaluation of the responses of different facets of functional diversity and structure across a regional rainfall gradient in Central Africa using data of

bird communities collected with a hybrid fractal design. We predict that i) functional community structure changes along the rainfall gradient with different functional strategies (trait syndromes) in the wettest and driest sites. We also test the hypothesis that ii) different facets of functional diversity have different responses to precipitation, temperature and their seasonalities. Particularly that functional dispersion and functional richness increase with precipitation and temperature, while functional evenness decreases with both metrics. We also tested whether their seasonalities decrease functional richness and divergence while increase functional evenness. We explored these relationships across spatial scales under different sampling scenarios using a nested fractal design. Finally, we assess iii) how after accounting for species richness these functional diversity metrics respond to these climatic factors. With our work we aimed to provide an overview of the functional structure of tropical rainforest bird communities along an Afrotropical regional environmental gradient and obtain insights into how the functionality of tropical animal communities is responding to current climatic conditions providing a benchmark for future responses to climatic changes in tropical gradients.

2. Methods

2.1 Study sites

Our study took place in an extensive rainfall gradient in central Africa in the Republic of Cameroon (Figure 1). We sampled four different and distant forest locations that represent different floristic clusters associated with varied levels of annual mean precipitation. Precipitation ranges between 2800 mm in Campo Ma'an National Park to 1500 mm in Lobeke National Park, with intermediate levels in the Dja faunistic reserve (1600 mm) and more seasonal conditions in Mbam et Djerem National Park (1800-2000 mm) (Table 1). These forest sites differ in tree species composition, and

forest structure as a consequence of climatic factors (Rejou-Mechain et al. 2021). Mean annual temperature is more constant across the gradient with a lower range of variation (Table 1). All the locations represent primary rainforest areas inside protected areas with very low or no human disturbance in forest cover, and we only focused in primary late successional forest and exclude from the sampling any other habitat type either natural (riparian forest) or human-induced (e.g., agricultural crops).

Figure 1. Geographic location of the four forest study sites in Cameroon (Campo Ma’an, Dja, Lobeke, and Mbam et Djerem) across the climatic gradient defined by rainfall. Dashed white lines show approximate distances between sites (km).

2.2 Climatic data

To cope with the uncertainty in climate estimates for central Africa (Akinsanola et al. 2025), we extracted climate data from four different sources (Table1). First, we extracted data from the WORLDCLIM version 2.0 database from 1981-2021 (Fick and Hijmans 2017) with a resolution

of 30 arc seconds. We extracted mean annual precipitation (MAP), mean annual temperature (MAT), precipitation seasonality (PS) and temperature seasonality (TS) for each point count per site. We also extracted values for MAP and MAT from the CHELSA+bioclim climatic database (Karger et al. 2017) using a temporal frame from 1981-2024 and resolution of 30 arc seconds.

To further assess the specific values for precipitation in the gradient we extracted data for monthly precipitation from CHIRPS dataset (Funk et al. 2015) which provides data of precipitation with a global coverage and 180 arc-seconds of resolution. We computed an annual value per point count from 1981-2025 and used these annual values to compute MAP.

Table 1: Summary of climatic products and variables used in the present study.

Gradient strata	Dataset	Variable	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Campo	CHELSA	Rainfall	3,077.7	25.2	3,026.6	3,113.1
Campo	CHELSA	Temperature	24.8	0.1	24.8	24.9
Campo	CHIRPS	Rainfall	2,315.5	23.5	2,282.7	2,331.9
Campo	CRU	Rainfall	2,549.5	0.0	2,549.5	2,549.5
Campo	WorldClim	Rainfall	2,320.2	7.0	2,303.0	2,323.0
Campo	WorldClim	Temperature	25.3	0.0	25.2	25.3
Dja	CHELSA	Rainfall	1,490.3	6.7	1,477.4	1,503.8
Dja	CHELSA	Temperature	23.5	0.1	23.4	23.6
Dja	CHIRPS	Rainfall	1,581.2	3.3	1,579.7	1,588.4
Dja	CRU	Rainfall	1,554.6	0.0	1,554.6	1,554.6
Dja	WorldClim	Rainfall	1,606.8	1.5	1,602.0	1,608.0
Dja	WorldClim	Temperature	23.7	0.0	23.7	23.8
Lobeke	CHELSA	Rainfall	1,468.5	15.8	1,446.6	1,494.7
Lobeke	CHELSA	Temperature	24.5	0.0	24.4	24.6
Lobeke	CHIRPS	Rainfall	1,596.3	7.3	1,592.4	1,609.8
Lobeke	CRU	Rainfall	1,655.2	0.0	1,655.2	1,655.2
Lobeke	WorldClim	Rainfall	1,579.0	0.0	1,579.0	1,579.0
Lobeke	WorldClim	Temperature	24.7	0.0	24.7	24.7

Gradient strata	Dataset	Variable	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Mbam et Djerem	CHELSA	Rainfall	1,837.7	21.3	1,795.2	1,873.0
Mbam et Djerem	CHELSA	Temperature	23.8	0.1	23.6	24.0
Mbam et Djerem	CHIRPS	Rainfall	1,740.2	11.4	1,734.2	1,761.2
Mbam et Djerem	CRU	Rainfall	1,562.8	27.9	1,548.1	1,614.3
Mbam et Djerem	WorldClim	Rainfall	1,605.7	2.9	1,603.0	1,612.0
Mbam et Djerem	WorldClim	Temperature	23.3	0.1	23.2	23.5

We also extracted climatic data from the climate research Unit source (CRU) (Harris et al. 2020). This only-weather station source is 1800 arc-seconds in resolution and we extracted MAP and MAT from the period 1981-2021 in order to compare with the other climatic sources. We computed an overall mean value for precipitation and temperature per point count for each point count per site based on the MAP and MAT from each climatic source (Table 1). These overall mean values we used in the models (see section 2.8).

To evaluate the spatial influence of our estimates, we quantified spatial autocorrelation (SAC) at the point count, cluster and site levels respectively within site and between sites using I moran tests. Test showed no SAC among sites or between clusters on each site (supplementary material table S1).

2.3 Bird sampling

In order to sample the bird communities in the gradient we used point counts (Buckland et al. 2008). We follow (Robinson and Curtis 2020) benchmark approach to create a network of point counts located to a regular distance of 300 meters (Figure 2). We implemented this approach within a hybrid nested fractal sampling design which is composed of a nested structure of triads (triangles) plus a hexagon of different sizes with a regular distance (300, 900 and 2700 meters) among points

(Figure 2). In total we have four clusters of plots (900 meters between them) with 10-point counts per triangular cluster and 6 points in the hexagon in each of our forest locations (n=36 point counts per location).

Within each point count across the gradient (n=144) we did 10-minute point counts in a radius of 100 meters. We made six replicates per point in order to increase the probability of detection of rare and cryptic species and we changed the order and direction of the surveys to visit them early in the morning. Points were conducted by an expert field ornithologist (FJM). In total we did 862-point counts across the four forest sites.

Figure 2 Hierarchical fractal sampling design used to quantify functional diversity across spatial scales. Four beta clusters (Beta 1–4) are distributed across each site (~2700 m apart), each containing alpha plots arranged in a triangular fractal configuration. Nested triads define different effective spatial grains (scaling factor) across four sampling scenarios.

2.4 Trait data and selection

For the present study we focus on traits that are known to influence the fitness of individuals (functional traits (de Bello et al. 2025) particularly in terms of their responses to climatic (abiotic) factors. Therefore, we focus on “response traits” rather than effect traits (de Bello et al. 2025; Diaz and Cabido 2001). While previous research tends to include as many traits as possible (Pigot et al. 2016; 2020), we did not include traits mostly associated with resource acquisition (e.g., beak morphology, length) which can be better considered "effect traits" (de Bello, Carmona, et al. 2021b; de Bello et al. 2025) under the context of our study and objectives. Also, we excluded traits strongly subject to sexual selection rather than climate per se (tail length) (Møller et al. 2006; Winquist and Lemon 1994), or those for which we do not have previous empirical knowledge of how they affect species responses to climate (e.g., nest types) in this specific type of gradients in the tropics.

We selected a set of traits that are known to be functional and associated with physiological and metabolic responses to climate in birds, in other words those mostly associated with their Grinnelian niche (Soberón 2007). Dispersal ability is a trait crucial for bird persistence across climatic gradients (Devictor et al. 2008; Weeks et al. 2023). Hence, we used the hand wing index as a proxy for dispersal ability (Sheard et al. 2020). Body mass is a critical trait that determines bird metabolic responses to climate (Ryding et al. 2024; Watson and Kerr 2025; Zimova et al. 2023). Tarsus length is a morphological trait associated with locomotion and movement, which has been shown to influence species foraging and movement under different climatic conditions

(Pigot et al. 2020; Ryding et al. 2024; Zimova et al. 2023). We extracted from AVONET (Tobias et al. 2022) species-level data for all these three traits.

2.5 Estimating functional diversity metrics and assessing the quality of the functional trait space

Functional diversity has many different metrics that encompass different facets of the communities under study. For the present work we focus on within-groups functional diversity (alpha), and on the facets of richness, divergence and evenness (Mammola et al. 2021). We also incorporate abundance data in the metrics (quantitative weight) (de Bello, Carmona, et al. 2021b; Magneville et al. 2022). Our sampling of 144 independent point counts, each replicated six times (n=862 surveys), ensures high confidence in *all* functional diversity metrics, surpassing stability thresholds for both raw indices and SES (van der Plas et al. 2017).

In order to explore how much trait space is occupied by the local communities (richness) we use Hill richness metrics (Hillric for $q=1$ and $q=2$) which estimates the effective number of functionally distinct species in a community, making them less biased than traditional functional richness metrics (Chiu and Chao 2014). For the divergence facet that explored the variance in the trait space of these communities, we selected functional dispersion (FDis) which quantifies the degree of dispersion of trait values (measured using weighted mean distance of each species) around the centroid in a functional niche space (Laliberté and Legendre 2010). For the regularity dimension which explores how regular are the traits distributed in the trait space (Mammola et al. 2021; Vileger et al. 2008) we used the functional evenness metric (FEve) (Vileger et al. 2008). For computing these functional diversity indices, we calculate a trait dissimilarity matrix for building the trait space. We used a matrix with trait values for our species pool (all species in the gradient, n=172) and a matrix summarizing species abundance per point count, using the package

mFD (Magneville et al. 2022). We excluded three species due to uncertainty in trait assignment and/or taxonomy. All three were extremely rare, representing only 1.6% of the species pool and a negligible fraction of total detections; therefore, their exclusion is unlikely to affect functional diversity estimates.

We log transformed body size before the analysis to avoid influence in the dissimilarity matrix (de Bello, Carmona, et al. 2021b). The other traits were scaled and approached normality making unnecessary transformation. However, in order to standardize traits to similar weights and units and reduce trait over-influence on the resulting dissimilarity matrix, we used the function *func.dist* to compute pairwise trait-based distances using adjusted Gower distances using the package *gawdis()* (de Bello, Botta-Dukát, et al. 2021).

The quality of the functional space is a critical aspect for the quantification of functional diversity metrics (Maire et al. 2015; Mouillot et al. 2021). Therefore, we evaluate the quality of the functional trait space for our trait data using the function *quality.fspaces* of the package *mFD* (Magneville et al. 2022), to assess the degree of deviation of the original trait distance and the final gower distances in the functional space (Maire et al. 2015; Mouillot et al. 2021).

Based in the functional space that had the highest quality, we computed two functional metrics (FDis, FEve) using the function *alpha.fd.multidim* from the package *mFD*. For the Hill richness metric (q=1 and q=2) (Hillric) we use the function *hill_func_parti* of the package *hillR* (Li, 2018).

2.6 Evaluating community functional structure

We characterized community functional structure using a species trait space defined by the first three principal components (PC1–PC3) of a PCA on standardized morphological traits (body mass, tarsus length, hand-wing index), which together explained 99% of trait variance and captured major axes of trait covariation (Pigot et al. 2020).

For each point count (α -level community), community-weighted means (CWMs) in PCA space were calculated by weighting species PC scores by their relative abundances, following the mass-ratio hypothesis where dominant species determine community trait positions (de Bello, Carmona, et al. 2021b; Diaz et al. 2007; Kleyer et al. 2012). This positioned each point count as a multivariate descriptor in species trait space (Kleyer et al. 2012; Sperandii et al. 2025; Yang et al. 2023).

To summarize functional structure at the site scale (Dja, Lobéké, Campo Ma'an, Mbam et Djerem), site centroids were computed by averaging point count-level CWM coordinates (PC1–PC3) within each site. These centroids represent mean site functional position, while within-site dispersion of point counts around centroids quantifies local functional variability (Sperandii et al. 2025).

Trait loadings (PCA rotation matrix) were rescaled so arrows extended to ~70% of the maximum extent of point count scores in PC1–PC2 and PC1–PC3 planes, following standard biplot conventions (Borcard et al. 2018; Legendre and Legendre 2012).

This approach enabled assessment of: (i) differentiation in functional structure among sites along the climatic gradient, and (ii) systematic shifts in community trait positions indicating potential filtering toward particular trait combinations. While this ordination framework supports subsequent trait–environment testing (de Bello et al. 2025; Kleyer et al. 2012; Lepš and de Bello 2023), such analyses were beyond this study's descriptive focus.

2.7 Calculating standardized effects sizes

Because taxonomic and functional diversity can be highly correlated, influencing patterns of functional diversity (Cadotte and Tucker 2017; Pavoine and Bonsall 2011) we calculated standardized effect sizes (SES) for the four functional diversity metrics per point count. Following (Cadotte and Tucker 2017) we calculated the standardized effect sizes as follows:

$$\text{standardized effect size} = \frac{\text{observed FD} - \text{mean expected FD}}{\text{standard deviation of expected FD}}$$

(1)

Where *observed FD* corresponds to raw functional diversity values of the metrics, mean expected FD is obtained from 999 permutations from the observed values per metric and SD is obtained from the set of mean expected FD values (Cadotte and Tucker 2017). We used SES values only with all the point count data (n=144) (full sampling scenario) and not the sampling scenarios with decreasing sample size (triad scenarios) because a reduction in sample size can make SES estimates unreliable (van der Plas et al. 2017).

2.8 Testing the effects of climatic factors on functional diversity metrics

In order to test the effects of mean climate (MAP, MAT) and climatic seasonality (PS, TS) on the different metrics of functional diversity, we fitted nested linear mixed-effect models (Tredennick et al. 2021). Functional diversity metrics calculated at the point count level were used as response variables.

Because our sampling design was spatially nested, we accounted for non-independence among observations by including two random intercepts (for site and clusters). This structure controls for shared environmental and spatial variation within sites and clusters while allowing inference on fixed climatic effects (Harrison et al. 2018).

For each functional diversity metric, we fitted two separate climate model blocks: a precipitation block, including mean annual precipitation (MAP) and precipitation seasonality (PS), and a temperature block, including mean annual temperature (MAT) and temperature seasonality (TS). We did not combine precipitation and temperature variables within the same model because these climatic domains were strongly correlated ($|r|$ up to 0.9), whereas correlations within blocks were

low to moderate ($|r| \leq 0.42$), allowing reliable joint estimation (Dormann et al. 2013). For each block, we compared a full model including both climatic predictors with a corresponding null model containing only random effects using likelihood ratio tests (LRTs). Model coefficients, confidence intervals, and marginal and conditional R^2 values were used to evaluate the strength and direction of climatic effects on functional diversity.

A typical model fitted in the analysis can be written as:

$$y_{ijk} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{1,ijk} + \beta_2 x_{2,ijk} + u_i + v_j + \varepsilon_{ijk} \quad (2)$$

Where:

y_{ijk} is the functional diversity metric for alpha plot k, within beta cluster j, at site i; β_0 is the fixed intercept; β_1 and β_2 are fixed-effect slopes for the two climatic predictors (e.g. MAP and PS, or MAT and TS); $x_{1,ijk}$ and $x_{2,ijk}$ are standardized climatic predictors; $u_i \sim N(0, \sigma^2_{site})$ is the random intercept for site, $v_j \sim N(0, \sigma^2_{beta})$ is the random intercept for beta cluster; $\varepsilon_{ijk} \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$ is the residual error. This formulation was applied consistently across all functional diversity metrics.

We fitted a similar set of models sub setting the data at different sampling scenarios under different effective spatial grain, i) third triad (n=108 point counts, 84 ha), ii) second triad (n=36 point counts, 28 ha) and iii) first triad (n=12 point counts, 9 ha) to explore how changes in effective spatial grain (our scaling factor) influence the relationship between climatic covariates and functional diversity metrics.

For each model we implemented a protocol for assessing their assumptions checking for overdispersion, multicollinearity, homoscedasticity, normality of residuals and outliers using the packages performance (Lüdecke et al. 2021) and DHARMA (Hartig et al. 2024). We fitted all the

models using the package lme4 (Bates et al. 2015). All the analysis was done in the r program (R core team 2024).

3. Results

3.1 Quality of the trait space

Our assessment of the quality of the trait space showed that three axes were enough to accurately represent the trait space of the regional gradient pool (n=172 species included) in the gradient. More dimensions did not represent any significant gain (Table 2).

PCA showed that the first axis that includes body size and tarsus length explained most of the variance (62%) in traits among sites in the gradient, while the second (33.3%) and third (4.7%) axis added a smaller variation related with HWI.

Table 2: Summary of variance explained by successive PCA axes and the different parameter to assess the quality of reduced-dimensional trait spaces in reproducing original trait distances among species. For information about parameters see (Mouillot et al. 2021).

k_axes	var_explained_k	cum_var_k	R2_dist	Delta_R2	Stress	Delta_Stress
1.0	61.99	61.99	0.7326	nan	0.3933	nan
2.0	33.28	95.26	0.9953	0.2627	0.0499	-0.3434
3.0	4.74	100.0	1.0	0.0047	0.0	-0.0499

3.2 Functional structure along the gradient

Community weighted mean trait values indicated systematic shifts in functional structure along the gradient (Figure 3). There were different trait-syndromes associated with the driest (Lobeke)

and wettest (Campo Ma'an) forest sites. In contrast, communities at intermediate precipitation levels exhibited more similar trait composition (Figure 3).

Across sampling scenarios (triad scenarios), functional differentiation among sites was consistently maintained (Figure 4). However, differentiation among sites increased at low effective spatial grain (second and first triad scenarios), where community centroids were more widely separated in trait space while occupying similar regions of the functional space. This indicated that the same broad functional strategies were retained across scales, despite changes at the resolution

in which the data is aggregated. In addition, communities from the driest site exhibited higher within-site trait variance, whereas communities from wetter locations showed more clustered trait distributions (Figure 4).

Third triad

Second triad

First triad

Figure 4: Functional trait space across sampling scenarios (triads). Functional trait space of forest bird communities projected onto the first two PCA axes (PC1–PC2). Points represent point counts (alpha plots) colored by site, and larger symbols indicate site centroids. Panels correspond to the third, second, and first triads (top to bottom), representing decreasing effective spatial grain within the same regional species pool.

3.3 Responses of functional diversity to the climatic gradient

Nested models indicated that climate effects on functional diversity were primarily driven by seasonality rather than mean conditions (Table 3, Appendix S1 Table S2). Within the water-related axis, precipitation seasonality (PS) had significant effects across multiple functional diversity metrics, whereas mean annual precipitation (MAP) did not show significant effects for any metric. Similarly, along the temperature axis, temperature seasonality (TS) exerted stronger and more consistent effects on functional diversity than mean annual temperature (MAT).

Table 3: Effects of climatic axes on functional diversity metrics. Model-level results. Significant climatic effects (LRT $p < 0.05$) are shown in bold. Detailed fixed-effect estimates for individual climatic covariates are reported in Table S2.

response	model	AIC	R2_marginal	LRT_p	Climatic axis
fdis	MAP + PS	- 465.522	0.332	0.002	Rainfall (MAP + PS)
feve	MAP + PS	-435.27	0.141	0.005	Rainfall (MAP + PS)
Hillric_q1	MAP + PS	841.816	0.273	0.005	Rainfall (MAP + PS)
Hillric_q2	MAP + PS	845.569	0.256	0.01	Rainfall (MAP + PS)
fdis	MAT + TS	-462.68	0.319	0.007	Temperature (MAT + TS)
feve	MAT + TS	- 435.273	0.141	0.005	Temperature (MAT + TS)

Hillric_q1	MAT + TS	840.894	0.278	0.003	Temperature (MAT + TS)
Hillric_q2	MAT + TS	844.535	0.26	0.006	Temperature (MAT + TS)

Climatic effects were strongest for functional richness metrics (Hill diversity $q = 1$ and $q = 2$), while effects on functional dispersion (FDIs) and functional evenness (FEve) were generally weaker (Table 3; Table S2). Predictions based on the nested models indicated that functional diversity metrics showed limited responses to MAP, MAT, and TS, whereas responses to precipitation seasonality were pronounced. Specifically, increasing PS was associated with a decline in functional dispersion, no consistent change in functional evenness, and increases in functional richness (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Effects of precipitation seasonality on functional diversity metrics. Predicted relationships between precipitation seasonality and functional diversity metrics across the rainfall gradient. Lines show model predictions with 95% confidence intervals. Significance symbols indicate whether the precipitation seasonality effect was statistically supported in the fitted models (likelihood-ratio test, $p < 0.05$). Detailed fixed-effect estimates for individual climatic covariates are reported in Table S2.

After controlling for species richness using standardized effect sizes (SES), the relative importance of climatic drivers shifted. Precipitation seasonality retained significant negative effects on functional dispersion and functional evenness, while its positive effects on functional richness were reduced (Table S3). In contrast, mean annual precipitation showed a positive effect on SES functional evenness. For the temperature axis, the influence of MAT and TS increased for SES-based dispersion and evenness metrics, but was strongly reduced for SES functional richness, indicating that richness-driven patterns accounted for much of the raw temperature–functional richness relationships.

3.4 Cross-scale effects of climate on functional diversity

Climatic effects on functional diversity were qualitatively consistent across the sampling scenarios. Precipitation seasonality and temperature seasonality showed consistent effects across functional diversity metrics, whereas mean annual precipitation and mean annual temperature exhibited weak or non-significant effects for most metrics (Table S4). However, effect strength varied for some climatic factors, particularly precipitation seasonality and mean annual temperature. Richness-weighted functional diversity metrics were more sensitive to spatial scaling, showing changes in both effect magnitude and statistical significance.

4. Discussion

The present work revealed insights into how temporal variance in precipitation and temperature rather than means influence the functional structure and diversity of animal communities in

tropical lowland climatic gradients. Our results suggest a more pluralistic approach when investigating the effects of climate on tropical biodiversity.

4.1 Functional structure variation along the rainfall gradient

Our study showed that the functional structure of forest bird communities changed along the climatic gradient. The distinctive trait syndromes we identified in different locations revealed that lowland forest bird communities are functionally much more complex than what was suggested in past global macroecological research (Barbet-Massin and Jetz 2015; Stewart et al. 2022).

First, we found that even in the same biome (forest) there are different combinations of traits associated with different levels of precipitation and its seasonality. A first syndrome represents bird communities with small-bodied, larger tarsi and limited dispersal in the driest location relatively close to the Congo river (Lobeke park). This suggests a community dominated by ground insectivorous and granivorous foragers. A second syndrome represents species with small to medium bodied-sizes with shorter tarsi and very low dispersal in the very wet Atlantic coastal forest in Campo Ma'an, indicating communities dominated by aerial foragers and leaf gleaners mostly understory insectivorous. A third trait syndrome reflects larger bodied-sizes, longer tarsus and high dispersal reflecting communities more dominated by large frugivorous (hornbills) and ant-followers in areas with intermediate rainfall but high seasonality (Mbam et Djerem and Dja).

Neither of these trait syndromes in tropical lowlands have been detected in previous macroecological research which tend to get very broad estimates of functional structure in tropical forests using species distribution models and polygon-based range maps (Leandro-Silva et al. 2025; Stewart et al. 2022). Therefore, our results suggest caution in inferring changes in community structure in tropical gradients without standardized empirical community ecology data that provide abundance and occurrence data from communities on the ground.

Our results also showed that these trait syndromes are insensitive to spatial scaling, with the same functional strategies remaining even after assessing the trait space under different effective spatial grains. Previous research in temperate forests suggested that functional structure is scale-dependent (Siefert et al. 2013). However, our study provides evidence that the detection of the functional structure of tropical bird communities is not influenced by the spatial scale at which communities are explored in contrast with scale-dependency in taxonomic diversity (Belmaker and Jetz 2011). This suggests that detected trait syndromes can be widespread in the different sections of the gradient as a consequence of climatic filters. Further research is needed to explore this possibility.

4.2 Responses of functional diversity to climate in a lowland rainfall gradient

Our study suggests that precipitation seasonality is the main climatic driver of change in functional diversity in Afrotropical lowlands forest bird communities. Contrary to our expectations and previous research (Albrecht et al. 2018; Gorczynski et al. 2021; Li et al. 2022; Ochoa-Ochoa et al. 2019), mean annual precipitation and mean annual temperature played a minor role in shaping bird functional diversity, suggesting that temporal distribution of water rather than its annual amount influences trait diversity in tropical lowland climatic gradients.

Previous research highlighted the influence of seasonality on shaping bird functional diversity specially in temperate regions showing contrasting effects of temperature seasonality on multiple facets (Keyser et al. 2024; Quimbayo et al. 2024). Our results showed that temperature seasonality played a role in influencing functional richness in the gradient. However, precipitation seasonality dominated the changes in trait space (richness, evenness and divergence). These differences are likely associated with the fact that temperate bird communities experienced very strong temperature fluctuations (wintering freezing), compared to lowland tropical bird communities that

experienced more variation in water availability and associated food resources (e.g., arthropods) (Karr 1971; Stiles 1978).

It has been long suggested that precipitation determines the geographic ranges of African forest birds (Chapin 1923). Our results provide indirect evidence that the amount of water influences these distributions and hence functionally distinctive species. We found that more seasonality promotes more occupation of the trait space probably because different trait values associated with dispersal allow birds to cope with water and food scarcity during the dry season. However, more seasonality also reduced trait variance (functional dispersion) and evenness indicating more clustering and regular trait spacing in the communities, suggesting that similar set of values are filtered by lack of water as is known in plants (de Bello, Carmona, et al. 2021a), or indirectly influencing important food sources (arthropods, flowers, fruits) (Vollstaedt et al. 2017). Because we are not aware of any study in tropical lowlands bird communities that have explored these functional diversity metrics and climatic covariates, it precludes a comparison with our results.

4.3 Influence of species richness and spatial scale on the relationship between functional diversity and climate.

Controlling for the effects of species richness showed that precipitation seasonality was still the dominant driver of functional diversity, highlighting its prominent role. However, the effects of other climatic covariates shifted, underscoring that to fully uncover the unbiased relationships between trait structure and diversity in tropical climatic gradients, standardized effects sizes are a requisite as has been previously recommended (Cadotte and Tucker 2017; de Bello, Carmona, et al. 2021a).

These results also suggest that communities tend more clustered with an increase in seasonality suggesting a role for abiotic (water) filtering in the transitional location (Mbam et Djerem) and

over dispersed on the wettest forests suggesting a role for competitive interactions (Campo Mann). While it is tempting and often incorrect to infer assembly mechanisms based only on trait patterns (de Bello, Carmona, et al. 2021a; Mayfield and Levine 2010; Münkemüller et al. 2020), we avoid making this without further independent empirical evidence for the operation of mechanisms across the gradient, and because relying on single functional diversity metrics for inferring mechanisms can be misleading (Guillerme et al. 2025).

Our study highlights the importance of explicitly accounting for spatial scale in the sampling design when examining relationships between functional diversity and climate along tropical gradients. Comparisons across sampling scenarios showed that functional structure and functional diversity were largely invariant across the range of spatial scales we explored, suggesting a strong and consistent influence of climatic conditions on functional diversity. In contrast to previous studies (Gaüzère et al. 2023; Jarzyna and Jetz 2018), we did not find that spatial scale strongly altered functional diversity–climate relationships at fine spatial grains. The pronounced scale dependence reported in these studies may arise from comparisons conducted across very large spatial extents (e.g., 50 km, 200 km, 800 km; Jarzyna and Jetz 2018), which integrate substantially larger regional species pools at continental scales than those examined along our gradient. Under such conditions, scale dependence in functional diversity is likely to emerge as data from multiple sites are aggregated at broader spatial scales.

At finer effective spatial grains (9–100 ha), our results reveal a strong and consistent response of functional structure and functional diversity to climatic factors. This consistency provides a robust basis for assessing specific response functions (de Bello et al. 2025) across forest bird communities along regional environmental gradients, particularly when generalizing the responses of multiple species to specific abiotic factors across spatial scales. Overall, our sampling design offers a

valuable framework for testing how spatial scale modulates climate–functional diversity relationships within regional gradients.

4.4 Limitations

There are some limitations in our study. First, we sample a small number of geographic locations in the gradient as a consequence of deploying large fractals inside remote tropical forest areas, implying more spatial replication can be needed to generalize the patterns of functional diversity responses we found. Second, we focused only on climatic factors, but patterns of bird functional diversity are also influenced by biotic interactions and habitat structure (Cooper et al. 2023; Dehling et al. 2016). Hence, quantifying these factors and the role in shaping functional diversity deserve more research attention. Finally, because of lack of trait data we used trait values from specimens from different populations (Tobias et al. 2022) to the ones we studied, ignoring intraspecific trait variations among and within populations (de Bello et al. 2025). A critical frontier in bird functional diversity is collecting more trait data from many different populations from unexplored tropical regions.

5. Conclusions

Our results provide evidence that temporal variations in rainfall and temperature are relevant for shaping trait diversity in tropical climatic gradients where altitude does not drastically change and hence temperature changes play a minor role. We found that distinctive trait syndromes emerged in forest bird communities associated with different climatic conditions. Therefore, projections of future trajectories of functional structure and diversity of tropical communities in regional gradients should consider temporal variations in precipitation and temperature and not only mean values to fully capture the spatial and temporal dynamics of functional diversity in the tropics.

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